

The Indiscriminate Use of the Term "Neuropathic Pain": Failure to Distinguish Between Definitions That Include and Exclude Nociceptive Pain

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Conflict of Interest:

The author reports that his child is employed by Nippon Zoki Pharmaceutical Co., Ltd., a company that manufactures and markets analgesic products, including tramadol, acetaminophen, tramadol/acetaminophen combination tablets, and Neurotropin®.

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the International Association for the Study of Pain, nociceptive pain, neuropathic pain, nociceptive pain, definition, questionnaires

From an etiological perspective, the International Association for the Study of Pain (IASP) classifies pain into three categories: nociceptive pain (NcP), neuropathic pain (NeP), and nociceptive pain (NpP) ⁽¹⁾. In 2016, the IASP first introduced the term NpP ⁽²⁾ and, in 2017, formally adopted it ⁽³⁾.

There are two conceptualizations of NeP: the unified NeP and the separate NeP ⁽⁴⁾. The unified NeP includes NpP, and the separate NeP does not include NpP.

NeP is often diagnosed using questionnaires. Most questionnaires, as well as objective diagnostic methods, had been developed before the IASP officially adopted NpP in 2017. Because NpP shares many clinical features with NeP, it is likely that some cases of NpP are classified as NeP in the context of these questionnaires.

Toda reported as follows ⁽⁴⁾: There are two conceptualizations of NeP: the unified NeP and the separate NeP. Currently, the same term NeP is used with different meanings. The term NeP in papers published before 2017 likely included the current NpP (i.e., the unified NeP). Therefore, the term NeP in papers published before 2017

thus differs from the current definition of NeP (i.e., the separate NeP). Caution should be exercised when interpreting the term NeP in papers published after 2017. If both NeP and NpP are mentioned in the same paper, the term NeP is generally the separate NeP. However, if only NeP is used in a paper, it is often difficult to determine whether the term NeP is the unified NeP or the separate NeP. As noted above, NeP in articles that use questionnaires to identify NeP is highly likely to represent the unified NeP. As a result, evidence regarding the prevalence, diagnosis, and treatment of NeP may be developed based on different conceptual frameworks, causing difficulties in accurate interpretation and comparison among studies. This confusion tends to be further exacerbated in narrative reviews, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses citing original papers. Similarly, the confusion tends to gradually worsen over time. This confusion is difficult to detect, and it is extremely challenging for non-specialist clinicians to recognize it. To the best of the author's knowledge, no published study has explicitly described the conceptual uncertainty arising from the simultaneous use of the unified NeP and the separate NeP. The most serious concern is that this conceptual uncertainty may go unrecognized, resulting in the continued accumulation of erroneous evidence and the entrenchment of an erroneous foundation for clinical medicine and basic research.

In fact, the statement, "If both NeP and NpP are mentioned in the same paper, the term NeP is generally the separate NeP ⁽⁴⁾," is incorrect. The term NeP used in previous papers cited in such papers may actually refer to the unified NeP. Consequently, the problem arising from the coexistence of the two definitions of NeP becomes even more serious.

NeP is an extremely important term in pain medicine. If the same term is used with different definitions, it will lead to serious confusion. An even greater concern is that very few published papers have addressed this issue. It is inappropriate to continue using the term NpP while leaving this fundamental problem unaddressed or ignoring it.

This is not limited to NeP. The definition of any term used in a single paper should be identical throughout the paper. When different definitions have been used because of historical or regional differences, those differences should be explicitly explained. It is inappropriate to use the same term with different definitions in a single paper without explaining the difference.

A serious and systematic effort is required to determine how the term NeP and NpP should be used in order to resolve the current situation in which the two definitions of NeP are used without distinction.

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